

Synthesis and evaluation of insect repellent activity of 4-amino-5-(4-bromobenzoyl)-3-ethyl-2(1H)-pyrimidone, on *Setophilus oryzae* (*Coleo curculeonidae*)

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Abstract : One pot synthesis of 2-(4-bromobenzoyl)-3-ethylureidopropenenitrile (**4**) was obtained by heating 4-bromobenzoyl acetonitrile (**1**), ethylurea (**2**) and triethylorthoformate (**3**). Compound **4** was cyclized to target molecule 4-amino-5-(4-bromobenzoyl)-3-ethyl-2(1H)-pyrimidone (**5**) by sodium methoxide. The insect repellent activity of **4** and **5** was evaluated on *Setophilus oryzae* (*Coleo curculeonidae*) at various concentrations.

Keywords : Insect repellent, ureidopropenenitrile.

In general pyrimidine nucleus have found applications in a wide spectrum of biological and therapeutic areas¹. In our previous communication² we have reported the synthesis of cytosine derivatives from the intermediate compound ureidopropenenitrile. The ureidopropenenitriles were obtained in two steps. In first step the benzoyl-acetonitrile was condensed with DMF-DMA to furnish 3-dimethylamino-2-(4-benzoyl)propenenitrile which on refluxing with urea or substituted ureas in ethanol for 3-4 h in presence of catalytic amount of concentrated hydrochloric acid furnished ureidopropenenitrile in 55-60% yield.

The ureidopropenenitrile **4** was converted to targeted molecules cytosine derivative **5** by refluxing **4** in sodium ethoxide for 1.5 h in good yield.

All the new compounds obtained were characterized by spectral and analytical methods. The compounds were screened for insect repellent activity.

The insect *Sitophilus oryzae* was reared in wheat seeds maintained at 27±2 °C, RH, 60-75%. Laboratory cultured adult rice beetles were initially taken for experimental purpose. The seeds of the rice were kept in oven at 80 °C to get free from infections. The disinfected and healthy seeds were smeared with 5-6 drops of 4 different concentrations of compound **4** and **5**. Experiment was carried out in 'T' shape glass tubes with glass vials. One vial filled with treated pulse, second vial contain water

Scheme 1

soaked cotton ball and third vial with five pairs of healthy beetles. Repellent of beetles were noted regularly for 24 h along with control. Percentage of beetles repelled lies between 20-40%.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Elemental analysis were determined on HOSLI C, H, analyzer. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Varin XL-300 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer model 298 spectrophotometer.

General procedure for the synthesis of 2-aryoyl-3-ureidopropenenitrile (4a-b) :

The mixture of 4-bromobenzoylacetone nitrile (0.01 mol), *N*-methylurea or *N*-ethylurea (0.012 mol) and trimethylorthoformate or trimethylorthoformate (0.02 mol) was heated at 65–70 °C for 30 min. The clear solution was obtained which immediately solidified. The solid after stirring in ether (30 ml) was filtered, washed with ether and crystallised from DMF.

2-(4-Bromobenzoyl)-3-methylureidopropenenitrile (4a) :

M.p. 198 °C (DMF), yield : 2.15 g, 70%; IR (KBr) : 3400, 3200, 2250, 1680, 1650, 1580 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.71–2.75 (3H, d, J 7.2 Hz, CH_3), 7.54–7.59 and 7.67–7.71 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.29 (1H, d, J 12.5 Hz, =CH), 7.15 (1H, bs, exchangeable with D_2O , NH), 11.70 (1H, d, J 12.5 Hz, exchangeable with D_2O , NH); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 39.00, 127.00–131.69, 137.00, 153.00 and 188.00. Elemental analysis calculated for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{BrN}_3\text{O}_2$. Calcd. : C, 46.77; H, 3.27; N, 13.63; Found : C, 46.95; H, 3.38; N, 13.60.

2-(4-Bromobenzoyl)-3-ethylureidopropenenitrile (4b) :

M.p. 180 °C (ethanol : DMF), yield : 2.15 g, 67%; IR (Nujol) : 3350, 3250, 2210, 1750, 1650, 1580, 1560 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : 1.03–1.08 (3H, t, J 6 Hz, CH_3), 3.22 (2H, q, J 6 Hz, CH_2), 7.14 (1H, bs, NH, exchangeable with D_2O), 7.59–7.62 and 7.72–7.74 (4H, d, J 8 Hz, Ar-H), 8.22 (1H, d, J 12.5 Hz, =CH), 11.84 (1H, d, J 12.5 Hz, NH, exchangeable with D_2O); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 14.65, 35.71, 63.94, 63.96, 126.06, 126.49, 128.57, 128.63, 132.83, 132.90, 150.93 and 154.57. Elemental analysis calculated for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrN}_3\text{O}_2$. Calcd. : C, 48.47; H, 3.75; N, 13.04; Found : C, 48.50; H, 3.72; N, 13.00.

General procedure for synthesis of 4-amino-5-benzoyl-2(1H)pyrimidone (5a-b) :

To a solution of **4** (0.01 mol) in dry ethanol (30 mL) was added solution of sodium ethoxide (0.23 g sodium metal in 10 mL dry ethanol) the reaction mixture was then refluxed for 1–1.5 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The product was isolated by aqueous work up by neutralizing the aqueous solution with 2 *N* hydrochloric acid. It was dried and crystallised from ethanol or ethanol : DMF.

Alternative procedure for 5a-b :

To the solution of **4** in acetonitrile catalytic amount of

triethylamine was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h (TLC check). The solvent was removed; the residue was triturated with methanol and kept overnight. The crystalline compound separated was filtered, washed with methanol and crystallised from ethanol : DMF yielded compounds **5a-b** in good yield.

4-Amino-5-(4-bromobenzoyl)-3-methyl-2(1H)-pyrimidone (5a) :

M.p. 281 °C (DMF : ethanol), yield : 1.69 g, 56%, IR (nujol) : 3400, 3150, 1610, 1570, 1500 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : 3.31 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.70–7.50 and 7.74 (4H, d, J 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 8.2 (1H, s, C_6H), 9.82 and 11.25 (2H, bs, NH_2); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 38.92, 131.70–133.56, 136.13, 171.60, 171.64 and 198.64. Elemental analysis calculated for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{BrN}_3\text{O}_2$. Calcd. : C, 46.77; H, 3.27; N, 13.63; Found : C, 46.90; H, 3.35; N, 13.63.

Synthesis of 4-amino-5-(4-bromobenzoyl)-3-ethyl-2(1H)pyrimidone (5b) :

M.p. 264 °C (ethanol), yield : 2.06 g, 64%, IR (nujol) : 3400, 3150, 1670, 1630, 1600, 1580 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : 2.45 (3H, t, J 6 Hz, CH_3), 5.29 (2H, q, J 6 Hz, CH_2), 8.80–8.84 and 9.02–9.06 (4H, d, J 8 Hz, Ar-H), 9.02 (1H, s, =CH), 10.15 and 11.26 (2H, bs, NH_2). Exchange with D_2O . Elemental analysis calculated for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrN}_3\text{O}_2$. Calcd. : C, 48.47; H, 3.75; N, 13.0; Found : C, 48.55; H, 3.71; N, 12.97.

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